

NILPOTENCY OF SUBRINGS GENERATED BY SETS CONTAINED IN THE MIDDLE NUCLEUS

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Abstract: Yen and Hentzel [8] studied the nonassociative rings with the ideal generated by sets contained in two of the three nuclei. In this paper we prove that if the additive subgroup S of a nonassociative ring R generated by commutators is in the middle nucleus, then $(S+SR)^n = S^n + S^nR$ for all positive integers n . Also it is proved that if $S+SR = S+RS$ and S is contained in the middle nucleus, then the ideal of R generated by S is nilpotent if and only if the subring generated by S is nilpotent. We use this to prove that if R is semiprime and the subring generated by S is nilpotent, then $S = 0$ and hence R is commutative.

Keywords: Non associative ring, Nuclei, nilpotent, commutator.

Introduction: A nonassociative ring R is an additive abelian group in which multiplication is defined, which is distributive over addition on the left as well as on the right, that is $(x + y)z = xz + yz$, $z(x + y) = zx + zy$ for all x, y, z in R . The commutator $[x, y]$ is defined by $[x, y] = xy - yx$ for all x, y in a ring. The nucleus N of a ring R , we mean the set of all elements n in R such that $(n, R, R) = (R, n, R) = (R, R, n) = 0$. The middle nucleus N_m of R is defined as $N_m = \{n \in R / (R, n, R) = 0\}$.

Throughout this paper R denotes a nonassociative ring satisfying $(xy)z = x(zy)$ for all x, y, z in R and S an additive subgroup of R generated by commutators such that $S + SR = S + RS$.

We assume that S is contained in the middle nucleus $N_m = \{n \in R / (R, n, R) = 0\}$.

Let $I = S + SR = S + RS$. By assumption $SR \subset I$ and $RS \subset I$.

We now prove the following Lemmas.

Lemma 1: If S is in the middle nucleus, then $S + SR = S + RS$ is a two sided ideal of R .

Proof: Let S be in the middle nucleus.

Then $I + RI = I + IR$. To show this we see that

$$\begin{aligned} IR &= (S + RS)R = SR + R \cdot SR \\ &= SR + RR \cdot S \\ &= SR + R^2S \subset I \end{aligned}$$

and
$$\begin{aligned} RI &= R(S + SR) = RS + R \cdot SR \\ &= RS + RR \cdot S \\ &= RS + R^2S \subset I. \end{aligned}$$

So if S is in the middle nucleus, then $I + IR = I + RI$.

Thus if I is either a right ideal or a left ideal, then I is an ideal.

Lemma 2: If S is in the middle nucleus, then $S^n + S^n R = S^n + RS^n$

for all positive integers n .

Proof: $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} S^i$ is an associative subring contained in the middle nucleus.

$$(S^i, S^j, R) = (S^i, R, S^j) = (R, S^i, S^j) = 0 \text{ for all integers } i, j \geq 1.$$

By induction, it is true for $n = 1$.

We assume the result for n . Then we get

$$\begin{aligned} S^{n+1}R &= S^n S \cdot R = S^n \cdot SR \subset S^n(S + RS) = S^{n+1} + S^n R \cdot S \subset \\ &S^{n+1} + (S^n + RS^n)S = S^{n+1} + RS^{n+1} \text{ and } RS^{n+1} = R \cdot S^n S = RS^n \cdot S \subset \\ &(S^n + S^n R)S = S^{n+1} + S^n \cdot RS \subset S^{n+1} + S^n(S + SR) = S^{n+1} + S^{n+1}R. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 3: If S is in the middle nucleus, then

$$S^n + S^n R = S^n + R S^n \text{ is the ideal of } R \text{ generated by } S^n \text{ for all positive integers } n.$$

Proof: From Lemma 2 we have $S^n + S^n R = S^n + R S^n$. If we replace S by S^n in Lemma 1,

we get the ideal $S^n + S^n R = S^n + R S^n$.

Lemma 4: If S is in the middle nucleus, then $S^i R \cdot S^j R \subset S^{i+j} + S^{i+j} R$ for all $i, j \geq 1$.

Proof: If S is in the middle nucleus, then by Lemma 3,

$$\begin{aligned} S^i R \cdot S^j R &\subset S^i R(S^j + S^j R) = S^i R \cdot S^j + S^i R \cdot S^j R \\ &= S^i R \cdot S^j + (S^i R \cdot R) S^j \\ &= (S^i R + S^i R \cdot R) S^j \subset (S^i + R S^i) S^j \\ &= S^{i+j} + R S^{i+j} \\ &= S^{i+j} + S^{i+j} R. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 5: If S is in the middle nucleus, then $S^i R \cdot S^j \subset S^{i+j} + S^{i+j} R$ for all integers $i, j \geq 1$.

Proof: If S is the middle nucleus, then by Lemma 3

$$\begin{aligned} S^i R \cdot S^j &\subset (S^i + R S^i) S^j = S^{i+j} + (R S^i) S^j \\ &= S^{i+j} + R S^{i+j} \\ &= S^{i+j} + S^{i+j} R. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 6: If S is in the middle nucleus, then $(S + SR)^n = S^n + S^n R$ for all positive integers n .

Proof: We assume the result for all positive integers $m \leq n$.

Then using this inductive hypothesis and the Lemmas 4 and 5 for all integers i and j , $i \leq n$ and $j \leq n$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{we get } (S + SR)^i (S + SR)^j &= (S^i + S^i R)(S^j + S^j R) \\ &= S^{i+j} + S^i R \cdot S^j + S^i \cdot S^j R + S^i R \cdot S^j R \\ &= S^{i+j} + S^i R \cdot S^j + S^{i+j} R + S^i R \cdot S^j R \\ &= S^{i+j} + S^{i+j} R. \end{aligned}$$

Now we prove the following theorems.

Theorem 1: Let R be a nonassociative ring and let S be an additive subgroup of R such that $S + SR = S + RS$. If S is contained in the middle nucleus, then the ideal of R generated by S is nilpotent if and only if the subring generated by S is nilpotent.

Proof: If the ideal of R generated by S is nilpotent, then $(S+SR)^n = 0$. From Lemma 6 it follows that $S^n + S^nR = 0$. So the subring generated by S is nilpotent. The converse follows similarly.

Theorem 2: If R is semiprime and the subring generated by S is nilpotent, then $S = 0$.

Proof: From Lemma 6 and theorem 1 we have the subring generated by S is nilpotent.

Thus $S^n = 0$. Since R is semiprime, $S = 0$. Hence R is commutative.

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